

PHARMACEUTICAL ACTIVE COMPOUNDS AND THEIR TRANSFORMATION PRODUCTS: A HIDDEN THREAT?

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1 Introduction

Organic pollutants released with wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) effluents into the environment can persist, bioaccumulate through the food web, and pose a risk to human health and the environment. Analytical methods sensitivity has greatly improved in the last years allowing the detection of more contaminants, including the so-called emerging contaminants. There are many different classes of micropollutants with pharmaceuticals (PhACs), including antibiotics, being one of the most important ones. These compounds are not always completely removed in WWTPs and therefore, they have been detected in the aquatic environment worldwide (rivers, seas)[1] and they may pose a risk for the aquatic biota. Pharmaceuticals have actually been detected in aquatic organism such as mussels[2] and fish[3] exposed to contaminated water. In addition, plants (including those intended for human consumption) irrigated by regenerated water can bioaccumulate these compounds (e.g. lettuce, celery)[4].

Moreover, the so-called transformation products (TPs) can be formed from parent compounds by means of biological and chemico-physical reactions in WWTPs and/or in the environment and in many cases, they are not detected as they are not targeted in analytical methods. Therefore, one of the current main challenges in environmental chemistry is the development of strategies to analyse them and study their presence and fate in the environment.

2 Methodology

A comprehensive literature review and prioritization exercise was performed and 65 pharmaceuticals (containing 15 TPs) were selected for monitoring. A tailored analytical method was developed by means of a Waters Acquity Ultra-Performance™ liquid chromatograph system coupled to 5500 QTRAP hybrid triple quadrupole-linear ion trap mass spectrometer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA) with a turbo Ion Spray source. This method was applied to analyse water samples from Greek islands in different matrices (WWTP influent, river water, sea water), to be compared with similar samples from Catalonia.

3 Results

The sum of all the detected PhACs and TPs concentrations (left) and the fraction of TPs over the total (right) are reported in Figure 1. TPs were present in all selected matrices. Influent wastewater had the highest concentration of TPs. Nonetheless, their concentration compared to non-transformation products its much lower in this matrix than in the river and sea.

Figure 1: Sum of PhACs and TPs for each matrix: influent wastewater, river and sea (log scale) (left)
Fraction of TPs over total amount (right)

4 Conclusions

A tailored method to detect and quantify both pharmaceuticals and TPs has been developed. TPs were detected in all matrices, with higher relative abundance in rivers and seas compared to wastewater. New methods are required to study their presence also in food and biota that can be exposed to them through contaminated water.

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Literature

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